

Photonics-based bi-band Radar for Sub-mm Displacement Measure

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Abstract—Radars based on Stepped-Frequency Continuous-Wave technique with differential interferometry are used for monitoring landslides and other ground failures, providing precise deformation maps of large areas. This technique is limited to the use of coherent sinusoids in a single and fixed RF band

Here a photonics-based radar is exploited to perform coherent multi-band differential phase estimation for enhanced displacement measures. Tunable operative RF carriers adapt the system to the environment and to the observation range. The system measured the differential phase over a synthetic band up to 7.4GHz. The experimental results demonstrate a precision < 200 μ m without using correction algorithms.

Keywords— *differential phase estimation, dual-band radar, microwave photonics, photonic transceiver.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Landslides and other ground failures are responsible for great damages. Radars have been exploited for controlling these ground movements, providing complete and precise deformation maps of large areas.

Commercial radar relies on the Stepped-Frequency Continuous-Wave (SFCW) technique with differential interferometry. It exploits several coherent sinusoids to synthesize a large signal bandwidth and to reduce the system noise for an improved measure resolution.

Currently this technique is limited to the use of coherent sinusoids in a single RF band, due to the issues in generating multi-band coherent signals. Moreover, the lack of highly stable tunable RF oscillators leads to exploit only a fixed RF band.

However, the capability to exploit coherent multi-bands would further increase the synthesized signal bandwidth, and would allow to tune the operative RF carriers for adapting the system to the environment and to the observation range.

Recently, the authors realized the first demonstrator of a photonics-based coherent radar, with the possibility of simultaneously generating and detecting several RF signals, in different RF bands guaranteeing an intrinsic high phase coherence.

This paper reports for the first time, the use of this photonics-based radar for a SFCW technique and differential interferometry based system. The intrinsic high phase coherence between the used bands avoids the use of correction algorithms. Moreover the use of a single photonics-based transceiver for generating all the RF carriers allows for a reduction of the whole system power consumption and footprint.

An accuracy lower than < 200 μ m over a range up to 3km has been obtained.